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**Proposed thematic issue of *Music and Data* journal:
*Interventions in the datafication of music in Europe***

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The thematic issue's title is *Interventions in the datafication of music in Europe*. Its articles are themselves interventions insofar as they introduce not just new music data, but novel methods of data collection and analysis that are reproducible by design. While currently applied in Europe, these methods could be transferred to any contemporary music ecosystem to fill critical gaps in the available data on their actors and interactions. Based on their findings, the articles also advocate for interventions in music data governance: i.e., multi-level decision-making processes about how music data are generated, collected, and shared. The thematic issue's aim is to nudge the ongoing and inevitable datafication of music toward greater representational, distributive, and procedural justice.

This concept arose out of cooperation between four applied-research projects on data in European music ecosystems. Three were funded under the Horizon Europe cluster "[Towards a competitive, fair, and sustainable European music ecosystem](#)": [Music360](#), [OpenMusE](#), and [FairMusE](#). The fourth – the [Live Music Mapping Project](#) – helped inspire OpenMusE on a methodological level. Our projects begin from the premise that contemporary "music ecosystems" (Music Moves Europe 2024) are characterised by complex interactions involving interdependent actors, resources, and governance systems – all of which generate data that could, in principle, be collected. While the term "datafication of music" is most often used in the context of digitalisation, ethnographic studies of oral traditions and Schenkerian analyses of scores also produce "music data", broadly defined. So do cultural access and participation surveys, structural business statistics, school education assessments, etc. A fundamental aim of our projects is to map the very wide range of music data – digital and otherwise – that exist and to identify which data are available to which actors, why, and how.

In this, our projects represent a lineage of EU and UK commissioned research designed to support "evidence-based policymaking": e.g., the *Feasibility Study for the Establishment of a European Music Observatory (2020)* in the EU and *Music 2025 – The Music Data Dilemma (2019)* in the UK, which found that some music data are simply not collected (e.g., basic statistics), while other music data are functionally inaccessible due to the lack of incentives for stakeholders to share them, the complex legal obligations that attach to them, non-harmonisable formats, non-interoperable systems, or a mix of reasons (see also the CICERONE project, Henriksson & Janowska 2023; the Measuring CCS project, Vilares et al., 2022; the [common European data space for cultural heritage](#) initiative, and the ongoing [Study on the Discoverability of Diverse European Cultural Content in the Digital Environment](#)). The express aim of this research lineage is to guide state data collection strategies in support of policy: the Culture Compass for Europe (COM(2025) 785 final) in the EU and the Creative Industries Strategy (2025) in the UK. Both policy agendas embrace "evidence-based policymaking" as a means of enhancing the economic competitiveness and, secondarily, the extra-economic value of national cultural and creative sectors and industries (CCSIs).

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Participating in top-down “evidence-based policy” cycles does not prevent our research teams from critiquing their limitations and the broader political-economic logics in which they are embedded. Indeed, it informs a unique perspective on critical music data studies. The existing critical literature is largely focused on theorising datafication and diagnosing its harms. One stream establishes the socio-technical and political-economic terms of the debate, with a strong focus on platformisation (Nieborg & Poell 2018; Meier & Manzerolle 2019; Prey 2020). Its recent capstone is Drott’s critique of the platform-driven decommodification of musical labour and the capture of music as an instrument of surveillance capitalism (2024). Another, largely quantitative empirical stream has focused on documenting user-side consequences of platform-led datafication. This has included “neutral” evolutions like accelerated genre emergence and hybridization (Whelan & Novak 2024), but also harms such as reduced diversity (Anderson et al. 2020), reinforced cultural inequality (Coavoux & Aussant 2025), and country representation bias (Lesota et al. 2024). A parallel mixed-methods empirical stream focuses on how music datafication happens, probing its infrastructures (Eriksson et al. 2019) and humanising the actors involved (Seaver 2022). Hesmondhalgh’s edited volume on *Music Streaming Around the World* (2025a) internationalises this stream of scholarship while considerably bolstering its methodological diversity.

The proposed thematic issue complements literature on the harms of datafication with a new stream of critical thought on how music stakeholders can mitigate, offset, and repair such harms. This aligns with Hesmondhalgh’s call to recenter “autonomy and agency” in music datafication research (2025b, p. 13). It also builds upon D’Ignazio and Klein’s demonstrations of how to seize the means of data production (2020). Drawing on the concept of “data governance in the public interest” (Huber et al. 2024), we promote “public-interest music datafication” as a corrective to platform-driven data enclosure. The articles in Section 1, *data for policy*, present novel data and methods for data collection and analysis that reveal unseen or undervalued music ecosystem interactions:

1. The introductory essay “Towards public-interest datafication in European music ecosystems” by guest editors Edwards, Rozbicka, and Gordijn defines the issue’s keywords and positions them within the critical music data studies literature.
2. “From map to mandate: Multi-layered music mapping and cultural decision-making” by Rozbicka et al. (Live Music Mapping Project) introduces music venue maps, layered with economic and transport data using open-source tools, as a scalable data infrastructure capable of informing cultural policy decisions. It offsets an imbalance in music data studies toward studies of recorded music, and especially of platforms (Webster et al., 2020).
3. “The praxis of music streaming: Lessons learned from GDPR-compliant data donation” by Sørensen and Henten (Fair Muse) analyses listening-behaviour data donations from hundreds of streaming users, of whom a subset were also interviewed about platform fairness. It is a methodologically pioneering complement to typical analyses of platform fairness using “big data” harvested via APIs (Dennissen & Bauer 2022).
4. “Toward a multidimensional model of musical value: Quantitative and qualitative living labs” by Leijen (Music360) develops a multidimensional model of musical value and validates it using quantitative and qualitative experiments. Like Rozbicka et al., it brings data-literate theories and methods to the study of a rich variety of non-platformised musical interactions.
5. “Background music in the foreground: Quantifying the psychological and economic impacts of in-store playlist localization” by Schoenrock et al. (OpenMusE) shows how algorithmic logics shape economic and extra-economic musical value in domains other than user-facing

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streaming (Drott 2024; Barth, Borgstedt & Edwards 2019) while also interfacing music data studies with theories of music and place (Bull 2007).

These methods are designed to be transferred, and could act as modules in a comprehensive music data collection strategy. We argue that the “EU Cultural Data Hub”, an initiative introduced but not yet elaborated in the Culture Compass for Europe, could pivot toward this strategy.

The articles in Section 2, *policy for data*, shift focus to legal and technical interventions to improve the accessibility of music metadata, which are crucial to tracking recorded music flows for both valuation and to assess fair market access and outcomes. Front and centre here is music data governance:

6. “Music metadata governance: A fundamental-rights analysis and ‘light-touch’ policy interventions” by Izyumenko et al. (OpenMusE) builds and empirically substantiates a constitutional argument for mandating music metadata transparency, then explains how this could be done in practice. It bridges music data studies with critical legal studies to show how datafication harms could be remedied (e.g., Katzenbach & Ulbricht 2019; Prainsack 2019; Huber et al. 2025).
7. “The Music360 platform: Decentralised data-sharing spaces as 21st-century music research and governance infrastructure” by Gordijn and Wang (Music360) positions decentralized data-sharing spaces as critical research infrastructure for current music ecosystems, and pilots such a space with six collective management organisations. It describes a technically and legally feasible alternative to privatized music metadata governance (Prey 2020).

Again, the planned EU Cultural Data Hub offers an implementation pathway. Izyumenko et al. build a legal case for platforms and CMOs to share metadata with the Hub, and Gordijn and Wang show how this could be implemented while respecting data subjects’ rights. An EU Cultural Data Hub built around metadata pooling and augmented with systematic data collection on live venues (Rozbicka et al.), streaming (Sørensen and Henten), cultural festivals and music therapy (Leijen), and background music (Schoenrock and Tautscher) would comprise a genuine public-interest music datafication infrastructure offsetting the “ruinous infrastructure” of platform monopolies (Campos Valverde 2025). In our introductory essay and throughout our articles, we argue that such an infrastructure could improve multidimensional justice in music ecosystems: it could help assess and support the fair distribution of resources, equal representation of actors, and inclusiveness of governance.

Viewed with respect to the *Music and Data* journal’s objectives, the proposed issue is the first coordinated scholarly intervention that treats music datafication as simultaneously a methodological challenge, an object of governance, and a rights-bearing infrastructure. A clear limitation of the proposed issue is its focus on Europe. This does not reflect narrow editorial interests, but rather the territorial scope of the four projects and, in the case of Izyumenko et al., the fact that the governance mechanism proposed is grounded in EU law. It should be noted that several articles target their interventions in part to support linguistic minority repertoires and/or foreground data from less-represented music ecosystems in Europe, such as Hungary, Slovakia, and Ukraine. Moreover, the coincidence of the thematic issue’s early-2027 release with the planned 2027 launch of the EU Cultural Data Hub makes the selection of geographical focus timely: the thematic issue’s critical contrast between the ideal of public-interest datafication and the actual tendencies of the state could counterbalance official discourse on the Hub. Finally, the methods and tools introduced by the other articles could all, in principle, be transferred to non-European music ecosystems (indeed, the editors are actively seeking funding to do this). The introductory essay will reflect critically on this limitation,

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engage with literature on non-European cases, and consider socioeconomic, socio-legal, and cultural factors in methodological transfer.

Finally, the guest editors believe that inviting a response essay per section by established scholars on the datafication of music would strengthen the thematic issue's positioning vis-à-vis the journal's objectives and readership. The guest editors would particularly welcome response essays that critically assess the state of datafication in non-European music cultures and markets, as well as the relevance of the articles' interventions (cf. Hesmondhalgh 2025a). We believe that our own dialogue with the respondents could act as a synthesising phase beyond the peer review of each individual article, helping ensure that the articles combine to tell a story of interest to the journal's international readership.

Commented [JE1]: @Tom and Stacy, this is new.

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